

Solvent Steric Effect in Keto-Enol Equilibria and its Quantitative Correlation with Alkyl Mass

J. M. JESSY* and K. JOBY THOMAS

Department of Chemistry, University of Calicut, Calicut University P.O., Kerala-673 635

Manuscript received 11 October 1990, revised 2 June 1992, accepted 22 July 1992

It has been demonstrated in an earlier work¹ that 'solvent steric effect' due to alkyl substitution is a very significant factor in determining rates of solvolysis though it is less than polar effect in magnitude. It has also been shown² that this solvent steric effect measured in terms of rate constants, could be correlated to a function of the reduced molecular weight of the solute and of the solvent with very good correlation coefficients.

The reactions studied for the above purpose were solvolyses of alkyl halides in solvents of lower alcohols—of both normal series and α -series. All the alcohols were of very nearly the same polarity as given by their dipole moments. In the present work, the same effect was studied in the same two series of lower alcoholic solvents, but for an equilibrated system in place of a reactive system; the quantitative measurement of the (solvent steric) effect was obtained in terms of equilibrium constants instead of rate constants. The equilibria chosen were the keto-enol equilibria of methyl and ethyl acetoacetates.

The alcohols are known^{3,4} to solvate the keto form in preference to the enol as the latter is stabilised mainly by internal hydrogen bonding, while the former, in the absence of hydrogen bonding, is much more susceptible to solvation.

where, R is alkyl group of solvent alcohol and R' is methyl or ethyl group. Therefore when steric hindrance to solvation is offered by bulkier solvent molecules, it was expected, in view of the solvent steric effect described earlier, to affect the stability of the keto form more adversely than that of the enol; the equilibrium was thus expected to shift towards greater percentage of enol. This shift should reflect in the change in value of the equilibrium constant which, in turn, would be a quantitative measure of the solvent steric effect on the system.

Results and Discussion

The results from the bromination experiments and the pertinent calculated values are listed in Table 1. It can be seen that the percentage of enol

TABLE 1—ENOL PERCENTAGE FOR METHYL AND ETHYL ACETOACETATES IN ALCOHOL SOLVENTS AT 35°

Solvent	Methyl acetoacetate		Ethyl acetoacetate	
	Equilibrium % of enol	K*	Equilibrium % of enol	K*
<i>Normal series :</i>				
Ethanol	8.455 1	10.827 2	10.806 3	8.253 9
n-Propanol	12.015 1	7.322 8	15.627 5	5.399 0
n-Butanol	14.685 2	5.809 6	18.287 5	4.468 2
n-Pentanol	17.948 5	4.571 5	21.113 8	3.736 3
n-Hexanol	20.915 2	3.781 2	23.773 8	3.206 3
n-Heptanol	23.585 3	3.239 9	26.101 2	2.831 2
n-Octanol	26.700 3	2.745 3	28.428 8	2.517 6
n-Nonanol	29.518 7	2.387 7	30.756 3	2.251 4
n-Decanol	32.485 4	2.078 3	33.083 8	2.022 6
<i>α-Series :</i>				
Methanol	6.230 1	15.051 2	7.481 3	12.366 8
Ethanol	8.455 1	10.827 2	10.806 3	8.253 9
iso-Propanol	10.828 5	8.234 9	13.798 8	6.247 0
Butanol	13.201 8	6.574 7	16.625 0	5.015 0

*Equilibrium constant $K = [\text{Ketone}]/[\text{Enol}]$.

steadily increases on moving from the less to the more bulky of the solvents showing that solvation, as the cause of stabilisation of ketone, decreases as predicted earlier with the consequence that the equilibrium shifts towards enol which depends little on solvation for its stability. The effect is clear along both the normal series (from ethanol through n-decanol) and the α -series (from methanol through t-butanol) of the solvents and for both the substrate esters studied. Thus, the results demonstrate the presence and significance of 'solvent steric effect' in the keto-enol equilibria just as in the solvolytic reactions of alkyl halides.

Secondly, on the basis of the linear correlation obtained between the logarithm of solvolytic rate

constants of the alkyl halides and the function $\log(1/\mu)$ (where μ is the reduced molecular weight of the substrate halide and solvent alcohol, given by $\mu = m_A m_B / (m_A + m_B)$, m_A being the molecular weight of the substrate and m_B that of the solvent), a similar correlation was tested for, in the present case, between the logarithm of equilibrium constants (in place of rate constants) and $\log(1/\mu)$ of methyl and ethyl acetoacetates, which are the substrates in the present case (in place of alkyl halides). Results show that the correlation obtained for both the esters in both series of solvents (the linear plots and correlation coefficients r , in Figs. 1 and 2) are very good, as good as those for alkyl halide solvolyses. It may be noted that in the case of

Fig. 1a. Plot of $\log K$ vs $\log(1/\mu)+2$ for methyl acetoacetate in normal series alcohols ($r=0.9962$).

Fig. 2a. Plot of $\log K$ vs $\log(1/\mu)+2$ for methyl acetoacetate in α -series alcohols ($r=0.9971$).

Fig. 1b. Plot of $\log K$ vs $\log(1/\mu)+2$ for ethyl acetoacetate in normal series alcohols ($r=0.9979$).

Fig. 2b. Plot of $\log K$ vs $\log(1/\mu)+2$ for ethyl acetoacetate in α -series alcohols ($r=0.9998$).

alcohols of α -series, the linearity of the plot is demonstrated by not more than four points because of the theoretical limitation that the series is made of four alcohols only.

Experimental

The esters, the solvents and other reagents were either purified by standard methods described in literature⁵ or of A. R. grade and were verified by boiling point and refractive index.

The estimation of percentage of enol in every case was done by bromination of enol following the direct bromine titration method⁶. The indirect method⁷ was found unsuitable as the liberation of iodine from the bromo derivative (on adding potassium iodide) was found to be of variable rate for the different (solvent) alcohols—being increasingly lower as the solvent was changed towards higher alcohols, for example, from ethanol to n-decanol (the liberation of iodine was not completed even after 24 h in n-decanol). The direct bromination

method gave consistent results even though it involved taking the bromine solution quickly and titrating fast, the whole process being completed within 30 s. Each determination was done in triplicate and the average value taken and the variations in values were less than 2.5%.

References

1. J. M. JESSY, *Curr. Sci.*, 1984, 53, 1025.
2. J. M. JESSY, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1987, 64, 126.
3. C. K. INGOLD, "Structure and Mechanism in Organic Chemistry", 2nd. ed., Bell and Sons, London, 1989, p. 799.
4. C. REICHARDT, "Solvents and Solvent Effects in Organic Chemistry", 2nd. ed., VCH Verlagsgesellschaft, Weinheim, 1988, p. 92.
5. A. I. VOGEL, "Textbook of Practical Organic Chemistry including Quantitative Analysis", Longmann's, London, 1968.
6. J. B. CONANT and A. F. THOMSON, JR., *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1932, 54, 4040.
7. Ref. 4, p. 792.